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The Histopathological pattern of lung cancer in Iraq

Abstract

Background: Geographical differences have been observed in the incidence of various histological patterns of lung cancer. Shifts in histological tumor type distribution, chiefly an increase in adenocarcinoma, have been reported to accompany changes in lung cancer incidence in the last two decades in the United States and several other developed countries.

No information is available about the frequency of various histological types of lung cancer in Iraqi patients. The aim of this study is to describe the histopathologic pattern of lung cancer in the largest series of Iraqi patients with lung cancer.

Patients and methods: In the largest series of 63923 Iraqi patients with various types of newly diagnosed cancer registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with the exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk) during five-year period (2000-2004), 5157 cases of lung cancers (4105 males, 1052 females) occurred in accounting for approximately 8% of all cancer cases in Iraq.

Lungs and the bronchi were the second most common site of cancer and the first most common site in males.

Results: The four commonest histopathological types of lung cancer are Squamous cell carcinoma accounting for 37.6% of the cases, adenocarcinoma accounting for 13% of the cases small cell carcinoma accounting for 8.3% of the cases

, and large cell carcinoma accounting for 7% of the cases.

Conclusion: The shifts in histological tumor type distribution, chiefly an increase in adenocarcinoma, have been reported to accompany changes in lung cancer incidence in the last two decades in the United States and several other developed countries were not observed in this large sample of Iraqi patients with lung cancer registered during five year period.

Keywords: Lung, Cancer, Iraq, Histopathological types.

Introduction

Primary lung cancer is essentially carcinoma of the bronchus. Occasionally cancer occurs in the trachea and pleura. Lung cancer is the leading cause (28%) of cancer deaths worldwide [1, 2] and accounted for 163,500 new cases of cancer in the United States in 2004 [2]. Compared with the other major cancers, breast, colorectal, and prostate has witnessed only modest improvements in its survival rates and clinical outcome up to the present time, and is the only major cancer type to have increased in the number of deaths annually [2, 3].

Histopathologic heterogeneity is a major confounding factor in lung cancer diagnosis and treatment [4]. Classically, lung cancer comprises three primary histological subtypes: carcinoid, small cell, and non-small cell, which account for about 2%, 13%, and 86% of lung

cancers, respectively. Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) is further subdivided into at least three histologic subtypes: adenocarcinoma (AD), squamous cell carcinoma (SQ)/epidermoid and large cell carcinoma. Small cell lung cancer (SCLC) is the most aggressive form of lung cancer, includes small cell carcinoma, mixed small cell/large cell carcinoma, and combined small cell carcinoma. Carcinoids (COIDs) form a distinct histologic tumor subtype that may secrete bioactive molecules, and are further subdivided into typical and atypical varieties [5]. Tumors such as adenosquamous and neuroendocrine carcinomas possess histological characteristics of more than one subtype, whereas tumors from the same histopathologic subtype may have dissimilar clinical outcomes such as drug response [6, 7].

No information is available about the frequency of various histological types of lung cancer in Iraqi patients. The aim of this study is to describe the histopathologic pattern of lung cancer in the largest series of Iraqi patients with lung cancer.

Patients and methods

In largest series of 63923 Iraqi patients with various types of newly diagnosed cancer registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with the exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk) during five-year period (2000-2004), 5157 cases of lung cancers (4105 males, 1052 females) occurred accounting for approximately 8% of all cancer cases in Iraq. Lungs and the bronchi were the second most common site of cancer and the first most common site in males.

Results

The commonest histopathological types of lung cancer as shown in table-1 are Squamous cell carcinoma accounting for 37.6% of the cases, adenocarcinoma accounting for 13% of the cases small cell carcinoma accounting for 8.3% of the cases, and large cell carcinoma accounting for 7 % of the cases. In addition there were 29 cases of tracheal cancer, histopathology is shown in table-2. For every 178 cases of lung cancer there were one case of tracheal cancer. In addition there were 31 cases of pleural cancer mesothelioma.

Histopathology	No (%)
Squamous cell carcinoma	1940 (37.6%)
Adenocarcinoma	672 (13 %)
Small cell carcinoma	428 (8.3%)
large cell carcinoma	361 (7%)
Epithelial tumor	240 (4.65%)
Oat cell carcinoma	130 (2.5%)
Carcinoma, undifferentiated	89 (1.7%)
Carcinoid tumor	19 (0.36%)
Carcinoma, Anaplastic	15 (0.3%)

Table (1): The commonest histopathological types of lung cancer in Iraqi patients.

Histopathology	No
Squamous cell carcinoma	19
Small cell carcinoma	4
Adenocarcinoma	3
large cell carcinoma	1
Carcinoma, undifferentiated	1
Squamous –small cell carcinoma	1

Table (2): The histopathological types of tracheal cancer in Iraqi patients.

Discussion

Geographical differences have been observed in the incidence of various histological pattern of lung cancer. Shifts in histological tumor type distribution, chiefly an increase in adenocarcinoma, have been reported to accompany changes in lung cancer incidence during

the last two decades in the United States and several other developed countries.

In Europe, the squamous cell type still predominates and an increase in incidence of adenocarcinoma has only been reported in the Netherlands. In Asia, in the 1960s and 1970s, the proportion of adenocarcinoma was higher than in North America or Europe and seems to be increasing [8].

In Varse lung cancer incidence rates in the period 1976-1992 overall, lung cancer had stopped increasing in males since the late 1980s, and had started declining in middle-aged men. Conversely, upward trends persisted in females up to 1991-1992. Although it decreased from 13 to 9, the male-to-female incidence ratio was, in 1991-1992 still substantially higher than in the U.S. and North Europe. Specific trends emerged according to histological type(s), with declines (males) or stabilization (females) for squamous-cell carcinoma and gradual increases for small-cell carcinoma in males. Adenocarcinoma was the only lung cancer type whose incidence rates increased similarly (2.5-fold) in males and females thus approaching, in 1991-1992, in the two sexes combined, the rate for squamous-cell carcinoma [9].

In Iraqi patients with lung cancer the changes in the incidence of squamous cell carcinoma and adenocarcinoma during a five year-period were very similar. Figure-1 shows the number of the registered cases of both histological types during five year period.

Figure (1): The number of the registered cases of both histological types during five year period.

Conclusion: The shifts in histological tumor type distribution, chiefly an increase in adenocarcinoma, have been reported to accompany changes in lung cancer incidence in the last two decades in the United States and several other developed countries were not observed in this large sample of Iraqi patients with lung cancer registered over a five year period.

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